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PAYMENT ASSISTANT

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Abstract:

Objective- Explosive growth of cloud services and web applications has made it impossible for users to manage dozens of passwords for accessing different cloud services. The situation is even worse considering the potential application of massively parallel computing devices such as GPU and ASIC for efficient password cracking. Motivated by a number of recent industry initiatives for online authentication, we present Payment Assistant, an innovative solution for password-less universal login.

Design/Methodology/Approach- Payment assistant aims to improve on passwords with respect to both usability and security. It takes advantages of push message services for mobile devices and enables users to access multiple cloud services by using pre-owned identities, such as email addresses, together with few taps on their mobile devices. It is resistant to the most common attacks on cloud services such as replay attacks and man-in-the-middle attacks. We also discuss possible extensions for protecting payment assistant from vendor lock-in and single point of failure, in order to ensure payment assistant to be an open and stable authentication system.

Findings- First main step is the web based client registration in order to get access to application. The application requests the user for one time registration process, user identity is checked by e-mail verification. It then requests PMS server to get pms credentials. Pms credentials and user id are sent to application server and in return the server provides OTP to confirm the identity and privacy, all details are protected by use of private key. All the registration details are stored and protected inside application server. The application of the proposed payment assistant security framework to the recent MintChip Challenge.

Practical Implications- System ensures user privacy and provides better security.

Keywords- MintChip Challenge, Loxin server, PMS server, Certificate Authority

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

The easiest and cheapest way of authenticating an end user, password based authentication methods have been consistently chosen by almost every new cloud service. The explosive growth of cloud services and web applications has made it impossible for users to manage dozens of passwords for accessing different cloud services. Our application provide an easy way of accessing the payment method in a secured and easy manner. Payment assistant aims to improve on passwords with respect to both usability and security. This app is resistant to most common attacks on cloud services. The application of the proposed payment assistant security framework to the recent MintChip Challenge demonstrates the power of payment assistant for building a real-world password-less mobile payment solution. Mintchip is a digital currency that provides the underlying system to facilitate the exchange of value between consumers and merchants in real-time.

II. RELATED WORKS

2.1 Image Captcha Based Authentication Using Visual Cryptography:

Many security primitives are based on hard mathematical problems. Using hard AI problems for security is emerging as an exciting new paradigm, but has been under explored a novel family of graphical password systems built on top of Captcha technology, which we call Captcha as a graphical passwords (CaRP).. CaRP addresses a such as online guessing attacks, relay attacks, and, if combined with dual-view technologies, shoulder-surfing attacks. CaRP also offers a novel approach to address the well-known image hotspot problem in popular graphical password systems, such as PassPoints, that often leads to weak password choices. CaRP is not a solution, but it offers logical security and usability and appears to fit well with some practical applications for improving accessible security. A fundamental task in security is to create cryptographic primitives based on hard problems that are computationally difficult. For example, the problem of numeral factorization is fundamental to the RSA public-key cryptosystem. The discrete logarithm problem is fundamental to the ElGamal encryption, the Diffie-Hellman key exchange, the Digital Signature Algorithm, the elliptic curve cryptography and so on.

2.2 Strengthening User Authentication through Opportunistic Cryptographic Identity Assertions:

User authentication systems are at an impasse. The most ubiquitous method – the password – has numerous problems, including susceptibility to unintentional exposure via phishing and cross-site password reuse. Second-factor authentication schemes have the potential to increase security but face usability and deployability challenges. For example, conventional second-factor schemes change the user authentication experience. Furthermore, while more secure than passwords, second-factor schemes still fail to provide sufficient protection against (single-use) phishing attacks. We present PhoneAuth, a system intended to provide security assurances comparable to or greater than that of conventional two factor authentication systems while offering the same authentication experience as traditional passwords alone. Our work leverages the following key insights. First, a user’s personal device (e.g., a phone) can communicate directly with the user’s computer (and hence the remote web server) without any interaction with the user. Second, it is possible to provide a layered approach to security, whereby a web server can enact different policies depending on whether or not the user’s personal device is present. We describe and evaluate our server-side, Chromium web browser, and Android phone implementations of PhoneAuth.

2.3 RSA SecurID Authenticators:

The RSA SecurID® system is relied upon by thousands of organizations worldwide to protect valuable network resources. Used in conjunction with RSA ACE/Server® software, an RSA SecurID authenticator functions like an ATM card for your network, requiring users to identify themselves with two unique factors something they know and something they have before they are granted access. More than thirteen million people use RSA SecurID authenticators to securely access VPNs, wireless access points, remote access firewalls, Web apps and network operating systems. The system is easy to use and manage and results in centrally enforced security with an immediate ROI in any e-business initiative. Each RSA SecurID authenticator has a unique symmetric key that is combined with a powerful algorithm to generate a new code every 60 seconds. Patented technology synchronizes each authenticator with the security server, ensuring a high level of security. This protection is priceless when you consider the risk of exposing critical information resources.

2.4 Captcha as Graphical Passwords- A New Security Primitive:

Anti-phishing mechanisms in the websites currently focus on helping users to verify whether a web site is genuine or not. Phishing on the web pages is an attempt by an individual or a group of threats/hackers trying to retrieve an individual's personal confidential information such as passwords, usernames/confidential info, credit card information etc. In this project, we are proposing a new approach named as "Image Captcha Based Authentication Using Visual Cryptography" to solve the problem of phishing. Textual keyword validation along with visual cryptography is a major advantage of this project. To increase more security "Blowfish Algorithm" can be used to divide the original image captcha into many blocks and rearrangement can be done. Then "Splitting and Rotating Algorithm" can be used to rotate the rearranged blocks. The use of visual cryptography technique((2,2) VCS scheme) is explored to preserve the privacy of image captcha by degenerating the original image captcha into two different image shares by manipulating the black and white pixel value of the image captcha. Part of the image share will be stored in the servers such that the original image captcha can be revealed only when both (client,server) of the shares are simultaneously available. The individual share images do not reveal the identity of the original image captcha. Once the original image captcha is revealed after merging different shares, which can be used as the password. Dynamically generating the Captcha image by the system is one of the major advantage of the system.

III.SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

With the advent of amazing cloud services and web applications, users frequently access services in their daily lives. Nowadays, we are likely to have more than ten accounts for computers, email accounts, websites, social networks, and various other cloud services, all with different passwords and security policies. Memorizing all passwords is both difficult and annoying, so people often end up in using simple pass words, or constantly forgetting less frequently used ones. It would be very useful if we can find an innovate way of accessing cloud services, which neither involves memorizing dozens of alphanumeric combinations, nor adds layers of complexity for users. For password-based authentication methods, their security is mainly determined by the difficulty of guessing a user's password. Unfortunately, passwords usually

have low entropy and are easier to guess than users think. The second piece of information is typically generated by a physical token such as RSA Secure ID or a software application as Google Authenticator.

DISADVANTAGES

- Need of two-factor authentication
- Painful registration processes
- Repeatedly Login procedures
- Poor accessibility

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

A naive way to reduce users' burden for holding multiple passwords for different cloud services is to store users' credentials in a single device or service, and use certain key derivation functions to generate temporal passwords for sequential logins. However, this approach exposes the authentication server as a primary target of attackers. Their evaluation results have demonstrated the difficulty of replacing passwords and highlighted the research challenges towards de-signing a password-less login scheme. In this contribution, we propose payment assistant, an innovative security framework for password-less universal login. After an initial registration process, Payment assistant enables a user to access multiple cloud services or web applications with only few taps on his/her mobile devices. This salient feature comes from the adoption of push message services for mobile devices and public-key cryptography. Different from most existing login solutions, the servers in payment assistant are not able to generate users' credentials. Therefore, even if a Payment server is compromised, attackers cannot impersonate a user in order to access cloud services. As a potential application of the payment assistant security framework, we have applied it to build a password-less mobile payment solution for tackling the recent Mint Chip Challenge.

ADVANTAGES

- Loxin servers helps in not to access user credentials
- Attackers cannot impersonate to access cloud services

- Solution for passwordless mobile payment process
- Users satisfaction and security.

- **SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION MODELS**

4.1 IMPLEMENTATION MODULES

There are 5 modules in our Payment Assistant application

1. Loxin client
2. Certificate authority
3. PMS server
4. Loxin server
5. Web Client

4.1.1 LOXIN CLIENT

A loxin app is created to act as a loxin client. Once the user installs the loxin app it performs a one-time registration process. The loxin app generates a pair of public key PK and private key SK. The loxin app prompts the user to choose or enter an ID and then sends ID and PK to CA.

4.1.2 CERTIFICATE AUTHORITY

The CA first communicates with the IDP and verifies the user's ID such as sending and verification email to the claimed address. If the user's ID is verified the CA sends its signed certificate Cert (ID, PK), containing both ID and PK, back to the Loxin APP.

4.1.3 PMS SERVER

The Loxin APP sends a registration request to a PMS. The PMS verified the request and sends back credentials for registration, which can be used by other software and services to send messages to the Loxin App. Here a simple token TOK to represent all PMS credentials

4.1.4 LOXIN SERVER

The Loxin App sends a registration request which contain Cert (PK, ID and Tok, to the Loxin Server. The Loxin server responses with a random number Preg and an expiration time T

for this request. The Loxin App signs ID, Tok, Rreg, T with its private key SK. This signature is sent to and verified by the Loxin Server. If the signature is valid the Loxin Server stores the pair (ID, Tok) into its database for later use.

4.1.5 WEB CLIENT

The web client here acts as a website that request authentication of a particular user so as to grant access to its services to the user.

4.2 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Step 1. Obtain a public-key certificate from CA.

Step 1.1 The Loxin App generates a pair of public key PK and private key SK. The Loxin App prompts the user to choose or enter an ID and then sends ID and PK to the CA.

Step 1.2 The CA first communicates with the IDP and verifies the user's ID, such as sending a verification email to the claimed address.

Step 1.3 If the user's ID is verified, the CA sends its signed certificate Cert (ID, PK), containing both ID and PK, back to the Loxin App.

Step 1 is only required to be completed once. After that, the user can log in to other cloud services by using this ID. Please note that the private key SK should be securely stored, and never be released outside the Loxin App.

Step 2. Register to a PMS.

Step 2.1 The Loxin App sends a registration request to a PMS.

Step 2.2 The PMS verifies the request and sends back credentials for registration, which can be used by other software and services to send messages to the Loxin App. Here we simply use a token Tok to represent all the PMS credentials.

Step 3. Register to the Loxin Server securely.

Step 3.1 The Loxin App sends a registration request, which contains Cert (PK, ID) and Tok, to the Loxin Server.

Step 3.2 The Loxin Server responses with a random number Rreg and an expiration time Treg for this request.

Step 3.3 The Loxin App signs ID, Tok, Rreg and Treg with its private key SK. The signature

Fig : Architecture diagram

V.CONCLUSION

We have seen various android payment applications with their features and compared with the newly developed android app “PAYMENT ASSISTANT” and concluded that this application will provide fast and secure services to its users related to any type of payment and recharge. It enhances the security by providing a Web Client registration to get access to the application. A number of technologies and standards such as Open ID and Oauth have emerged to deliver an Internet-scale identity system during the past few years. Their evaluation results

have demonstrated the difficulty of replacing passwords and highlighted the research challenges towards de-signing a password-less login scheme. Transactions can be done faster by storing details in the server database. Hence we are concluding that Payment Assistant App will provide a revolutionary step to the payment mechanisms.

VI. REFERENCE

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